

THE RELEVANCE OF FRENCH LANGUAGE TO NATION BUILDING IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nation building is not a simple task, it is a collective effort put together by everybody in all strata of the society. No nation is ever built around one area or sphere of human endeavour. While embarking on the Herculean task of building, language matters a lot because during the process of building, the builders must communicate. Looking at Nigeria with all her neighbours French speaking countries, we need to interact with these francophone neighbours, France and other francophone countries in terms of linguistic co-operation and bilateral relations. This paper therefore examines the place of French language in building the nation Nigeria; its importance and benefits to the citizenry. The paper recommends amongst other things that French language be given priority attention in Nigeria Educational system so as to equip Nigerians with the basic working implement for building the nation Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: French, economic, social, political, cultural, linguistic, scientific, technological, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

To build a nation entails channeling all resources together to give the citizens of that country a better life. The resources we mean here range from economic, social, political, cultural, linguistic, scientific, technological, natural etc. No nation is ever built without communication. Language plays a vital role in the nation building process. There are policies to be made both internal and external and all must be documented with language. The blue print which contains the architectural design of the structure to be built for instance is always interpreted with language. The business transaction and interactions with other countries involve the use of language. We know that no country however rich as it may be cannot possess all the resources it needs to build its nation hence the fundamental basis of International Trade Dewett (2005).

Considering Nigeria's tremendous mineral resources and natural endowments we must do business with our francophone neighbours. In the light of the above, there is the dire need for French language to be integrated into the building plan as entrenched in the words of the late head of state of Nigeria, General Sani Abacha on December 14th 1996 as quoted by Ade Ojo in Onyemelukwe (2004:20).

“We have seen that we are virtually surrounded by French speaking countries and these countries are our kith and kin. But, because of the difference inherited in language of our colonial masters, there is a vacuum in communication with our neighbours. It is our interest to learn French.”

This statement highlights the importance of French language in building a virile and viable nation. We need co-operation with our neighbours in its entirety to build the nation regionally, economically, linguistically culturally, etc. Nigeria's bilateral relations and partnership with France – a leading business partner with Nigeria and a world economic power makes French important trying to build this nation.

Aims and objectives

- (i) To show the importance of French language in nation building in an Anglophone country surrounded by Francophone countries.
- (ii) To highlight the importance of a second international language in this era of globalization.
- (iii) To highlight the relationship between international language on one side and unity, political and economic stability on the other side in a country with vast array of indigenous languages and culture

The notion of nation building

Nation building according to Wales (2010) is the process of constructing or structuring a national identity using the power of the state. This process aims at the unification of the people within the state so that it remains politically stable and viable in the long run. Nation building can involve the use of propaganda or major infrastructure development to foster social harmony and economic growth.

Nation building includes the creation of national paraphernalia such as national flags, national anthems, national days, national stadia, national airlines, national language and national myth. However at a deeper level national identity needed to be deliberately constructed by molding different groups into a nation especially in the case of Nigeria with its vast array of indigenous languages as opined by Caviedes (2003)

Why French language in nation building in Nigeria?

Nigeria will be doomed if it tries to build a national identity without considering its immediate neighbours, the sub-region and the international community. How can we jettison aside with levity the exigency of communicating with our neighbours or transacting business with them?

What will be the basis of communication? What language can Nigeria and its neighbours use to distinguish themselves from two blind, deaf and dumb trying to communicate with each other? The problem is a dual facet problem and the solution can be proffered on one side. We cannot wait for our neighbours to learn English language before we can do business with them effectively. This is as a result of a lot of factors which we believe are obvious.

Firstly, Nigeria as the giant of Africa really needs to bestride Africa like a colossus starting from its neighbours. If we must assume the role of leadership in Africa and to stamp our authority and supremacy in all spheres of life we must be fluent, effective and proficient in the two most dominant official languages in Africa (English and French) one, of which we already have by virtue of inheritance from our colonial masters Britain Onyemelukwe (2004).

Secondly, globalization has issued a non-restriction order to every frontier, giving access to everyone to do business anywhere in the world without hitches. There is no business that can be transacted without language. French language is one of the dominating languages in the world in terms of business, medicine, technology, science, computer, arts and culture etc. Nigeria therefore needs to incorporate the language so as to meet up with the growing challenges of globalization.

Thirdly, one of the yardsticks to measure 21st century compliance in no distant time perhaps is going to be French language in Nigeria. In fact, if you are not French literate shortly, the millennium will have no place for you. It is obvious that with the growing number of graduates flooding the job market with very many of them 'half baked' those with knowledge of French have an added advantage. In no distant time, from now, French language and computer will be the most important requirement for employment into very many establishments.

As Nigeria spreads its business ventures abroad especially across our borders we need dedicated and committed Nigerians who can be the eye of Nigeria over these businesses abroad. Can you imagine the difficulties if these ambassadors will face if they are not French literate.

French language, politics and regional cooperation

For Nigeria to maintain its lead in African politics and for her to remain the hub of geo-politics in the African continent, we have to elaborately co-operate with our neighbours and other countries especially the francophone countries by incorporating French language as an integral part of building our national identity.

Regional cooperation is also very necessary to avoid crisis and sometimes to resolve border disputes, conflicts, trans-border smuggling and other crimes. This cannot be achieved without bilateral talks between the affected countries. It will be more disheartening and absolutely problematic if by trying to resolve disputes and conflicts both parties do not understand each other not on the crux of the matter but by the barrier created by language. This can lead to disintegration and further complication of the issue on ground. We believe that that was Nigeria conceded some of its land around Bakassi area to the Cameroonians because a good deal was not struck because of language

barrier. Peace keeping missions and conflict resolutions become painfully impossible and regional cooperation becomes truncated without the knowledge of French language.

French language and economic cooperation

For Nigeria economy to receive a boost outside the oil and gas industry, we need to tap the resources we think are not necessary, unuseful and meager looking. This could be found in the way of business transaction with other countries. Take for instance the telecommunication business and the banking sector taken outside our borders could be very lucrative business. This will be very easy with the English speaking countries because of the language advantage that we have. But this can also be carried out too with the French speaking countries as expressed by Emordi (2007). If we have the basic knowledge of French strong enough to transact business with francophone countries, why distrust them for cheating, defrauding and swindling us thereby making us to shy away from doing profitable business that could catapult our economy to the next level?

To build the nation we must build our economy, it is a pivotal instrument for progress peace and stability on which platform development can stand. Also, if we must build our economy, we must build a language with which our nation can communicate economically with other countries as it is opined by Madueke (2007). The era of looking for interpreters; some of whom are dubious is gradually fading away. If we have the knowledge of the French language then why look for the services of an interpreter.

To consolidate the Franco- Nigerian economic co-operation which has existed before the late 70's which has also contributed immensely to the building of this country economically we need to do more in terms of strengthening economic ties with these countries.

FRENCH LANGUAGE AND EDUCATION

The aim of learning French language in Nigeria is not just only to contribute to the education of the individual by giving him access to the culture of a group of people he doesn't have daily contact with Wilkins (1973:154), but to increase the ease of contact and communication with French language speakers inside and outside the country through phone calls, internet, post, reports invoices, orders, memoranda etc as contained in the definition of communication by Kure (2001:216).

The acquisition of and the ability to us language is one of the most impressive process of learning that an individual achieves during the course of his life time Madueke (2007:2). How essential would this be if this language will be French language in this our present circumstances in Nigeria where we don't understand our neighbours. This type of acquisition goes a long way in helping nation building

There is the need to re-educate more people including adults who have long left school in form of mass literacy programme to acquire French language to give more value to their lives in this era of globalization. Looking at our neighbouring countries in terms of communication needs, French should be the language to be given special consideration in our primary and tertiary institutions.

According to Ukala (2008) "the product of education is knowledge." but the pertinent question is knowledge for what? The knowledge to building the nation. When people are educated they acquire greater skills and ability (physical and mental) for creativity responsibility and psychological well-being. Onyemelukwe (2004) categorically states that French language is a vital instrument for nation building and therefore indispensable to Nigeria.

The above statement by Onyemelukwe has communicated volumes of information about the status of French language and nation building in Nigeria if not that Nigeria has the problem of implementation its educational policies are effective enough to accommodate the 10 years master plan proposed by the presidential task force set up by the then military administration of General Sani Abacha in 1997. If that was done, a large percentage of Nigerians would have been French literate by now. Federal Republic of Nigeria (1998:9) has it spelt out like this: "government appreciates the importance of language as a means of promoting social interaction and national cohesion and preserving cultures... accordingly, French shall be second official language in Nigeria and it shall be compulsory in schools.

THE FRANCO-NIGERIAN LINGUISTIC CO-OPERATION

One of the areas of building the nation in French language is the Franco-Nigeria linguistic co-operation. France has contributed a lot to the building of Nigeria. The various French language centres, Alliance Française, all the Departments of French in Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Universities, Nigeria Association of French Teachers (N.A.F.T.), Nigeria University French Teachers Association, all play a part in the nation building as far as French language is concerned in Nigeria. These also contribute immensely to the Franco- Nigerian linguistic co-operation. The French Oil Companies like Total, Elf (TOTALFINAELF) and other companies like Peugeot Association of Nigeria (PAN) all play their roles in this co-operation to build this country as stated by Onyemelukwe (2004).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, nation building demands a lot of efforts. All strata of the society, people of all works of life take part in this process. In Nigeria, we definitely cannot build well without French language as language is the vehicle for communication. To communicate with our neighbours in business transaction and other forms of co-operation, we need French language to achieve the motive of building this nation. With the present trend of globalization the knowledge of French language is absolutely an added advantage for Nigerians to effectively build their nation as all her neighbours are French speaking countries. French language will now create an enabling environment conducive for interactions and business transactions with our neighbours, the francophone countries and members of the international community.

RECOMMENDATION

French language should be given more priority attention in the three tiers of education in fulfillment of the recent national policy on Education. This should start from the primary schools, adult education, and secondary schools so that within a short time we can achieve our goal of building.

Graduates of Polytechnics, Colleges Education and Universities should be re-educated to acquire certificates at French language centres and Alliance Française to increase French literacy in the country as we have in computer.

French language should be made compulsory in all secondary schools in this country from JSS1-SS2 and at first year of all tertiary institutions.

The Federal Government of Nigeria should give scholarship to those who intend to study French at the tertiary institution. This should include a trip to France for one year abroad programme to encourage participation and commitment.

More French teachers should be trained and employed with high remunerations and incentives. This will bring out French graduates who are either self-employed or working outside the teaching profession. This should be done in conjunction with the French and Belgian governments to enhance and promote the Franco-Nigerian co-operation which is symbiotic.

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